

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

Evaluation of Control FESOM hindcast (1979-present)

Deliverable D1.7

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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable is an evaluation of the hindcast simulations performed with the Finite volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2). We start with a brief description of the circumpolar ocean close to the continent followed by a short model description before we dive into a comparison with products derived from observations.

The Southern Ocean is the source of the Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW), a dense water mass that occupies 60 % of the global ocean. AABW is formed in different places around Antarctica (e.g. Thompson et al. 2018) as a mixture of High Salinity Shelf Water (HSSW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and, sometimes, Ice Shelf Water (ISW).

CDW occupies the deep Southern Ocean at depths between 200-1500 m, and is considerably warmer (temperature higher than 0°C) than the water masses found at similar depths over the continental shelf. CDW is carried eastward around the continent by the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) but close to the shelf break it flows westward within the Antarctic Slope Current (ASC).

The ASC is a quasi-circumpolar feature that starts in the Bellingshausen Sea and vanishes next to the Antarctic Peninsula in the Weddell Sea (Fig. 1). This current influences key processes on the continental shelf such as the melting of ice shelves and the formation of AABW (Thompson et al. 2018). Our understanding of how the ASC is connected to the flooding of the continental shelf with CDW modified by the interaction with local surface waters (modified CDW – mCDW) has improved since the review of the dynamical aspects governing the ASC by Thompson et al. in 2018 (e.g. Morrison et al. 2020) and revealed how complex and inhomogeneous this system is. Despite the differences, all studies agree that the presence of mCDW over the continental shelf represents a risk for the ice shelves fringing the Antarctic continent.

The water originating from melting at the base of the ice shelves, Glacial Melt Water (GMW), is fresh, cold and light and its presence in the surface layer can dampen the formation of HSSW (e.g. Silvano et al. 2018). The near-surface freshwater partly counterbalances the amount of salt (brine) rejected during sea ice formation, resulting in less dense surface waters that reduce the deep convection potential (necessary for the formation of HSSW). When there is strong and/or recurring sea ice formation, primarily in polynyas, a salty water mass with temperatures near the surface freezing point is formed and cascades down to the ocean floor (deep convection). This process is mostly observed over the continental shelf, and the resulting water mass is termed HSSW.

HSSW can flow offshore and slide down the continental slope mixing with ambient waters along its path until it reaches the equilibrium depth as AABW. HSSW can also flow underneath the ice shelf cavity and reach the grounding line where the freezing temperature is lower than at the surface due to the pressure effect. There it causes melting and the mixture with GMW generates the supercooled (colder than surface freezing temperature) and slightly fresher Ice Shelf Water (ISW). ISW can mix with ambient waters forming a dense water type that sinks when it reaches the continental slope producing another type of AABW.

When the dense shelf waters (DSW), either of HSSW or ISW origin, leave the continental shelf they are carried westward by the ASC together with CDW and lighter waters influenced by GMW. Part of the waters on the continental shelf are advected in the same direction by the Antarctic Coastal Current (ACoC), a westward flow observed in various sites around Antarctica (e.g. Schubert et al. 2021). The waters transported by the ACoC and ASC can have an impact on the neighbouring basins (Nakayama et al. 2014, Schubert et al. 2021).

In the following we will evaluate the performance of our Finite volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2) that aims at reproducing the above-mentioned key characteristics around the Antarctic continent. The model uses a global grid with highest resolution under the ice shelf cavities (2 km) and on the continental shelves (around 4 km). For our evaluation, we compare our model output with observations-based data products.

Fig. 1: Model mean absolute velocity below 100m depth overlaid by a schematic representation of the Antarctic slope current, Weddell Gyre and Ross gyre from Thompson et al. 2018. The dashed line is the 1000 m isobath.

2. Work performed and main achievements

“The Finite volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2) is a multi-resolution ocean general circulation model that solves the equations of motion describing the ocean and sea ice using finite-volume methods on unstructured computational grids. The model is developed and operated by the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), in Bremerhaven, Germany.” (quoted from the FESOM2 documentation, <https://fesom2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>, Danilov et al. 2017, Danilov et al. 2015). The interaction with the ice shelf is based on the three-equation approach proposed by Hellmer and Olbers (1989). The heat exchange is applied as temperature changes while the freshwater input related to ice shelf melt and the water freezing are handled as salinity changes. Temperature and salinity are modified only in the layers in direct contact with the ice shelf base.

2.1 Model Configuration

The mesh used for this study was generated using the FESOM Mesh Generator (fmesh - <https://github.com/FESOM/fmesh>) modified to include the ice shelf cavities. The global mesh contains 1,261,056 triangles (elements) formed by 648,389 vertices (nodes). ~36% of those are located south of 60 °S where the resolution (square root of element area) varies between 39.3 and 2.2 km with higher resolution in the ice shelf cavities and on the continental shelves and lowest resolution in areas with greater depth and few bathymetric features (Fig. 2). The bathymetry and ice shelf draft are derived from RTopo-2 (Schaffer et al., 2016). The vertical discretization was made with 148 horizontal “z” levels. The layer thickness is smaller near the surface and is kept constant or slightly increased with depth, the layer below has a maximum thickness increase of 10 %, for example if the layer on top is 20 m thick the layer below would be equal or 22 m thick.

The ocean initial temperature and salinity are from the “Global Ocean Hydrography with a High Quality Arctic Ocean Version 3.0” (Steele et al, 2001), a climatology derived from the 1998 version of the World Ocean Atlas (Antonov et al. 1998, Boyer et al. 1998). All the initial velocities are 0. The atmospheric forcing for the model is obtained from the Japanese 55-year Reanalysis, or JRA-55 (Kobayashi et al. 2015, Harada et al. 2016). The simulation starts in 1958 and goes until 2020 with 2-minute time steps; the outputs are provided as monthly means.

After 10 years of simulation, we started a set of passive tracers devised to assist in the investigation of the connectivity between different basins. They are 12 tracers for GMW concentration and 2 tracers related to sea ice. Every time step, the GMW concentration at the ice shelf base is increased based on the basal melt rate (volume of freshwater added divided by the volume associated with the node). There is one tracer that accounts for all ice shelves combined, while the other 11 reflect selected regions, e.g. Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf (FRIS), Larsen-C Ice Shelf (LIS-C) or the Ross Ice Shelf (RIS), see Table 1 for a complete list. The freshwater input from sea ice melt is also traced and when the salinity is increased due to the brine rejection a tracer proportional to this change is added.

Fig. 2: Model horizontal (top left) and vertical (right) resolution. Please notice that the X-axis on the right figures vary with depth (Y-axis). Map with ice shelves location where the passive tracer start (bottom left) in blue, cyan and green, the remaining colours are bathymetry. The red acronyms are for Weddell Sea (WS), CooperationSea (CS), Ross Sea (RS), Amundsen Sea (AS), and Bellingshausen Sea (BS). See Table 1 for the remaining abbreviations.

Ref. nr,	Tracer Name	Region
501	All	all ice shelves
502	RIS	Ross Ice Shelf
503	FRIS	Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf
504	LIS-C	Larsen C Ice Shelf

505	EWIS	Easter Weddell Ice shelves
506	Am	Amery Ice Shelf
507	GW	George VI and Wilkins
508	Ge	Getz Ice Shelf
509	PIG	Pine Island
510	Ab	Abbott Ice Shelf
511	SN	Sulzberger and Nickerson Ice Shelf
512	ABS	Amundsen and Bellingshausen Sea ice shelves
513	Fi	Fimbul Ice Shelf
520	Brine	salt from brine rejection
521	SIM	Sea ice melting

Table. 1: Passive tracer list with reference number used in the model output (left), the tracer name suggested for tracer use (middle) and the corresponding ice shelves (right).

2.2 Model Results

The main dynamical aspects required for the circumpolar connectivity studies proposed in OCEAN:ICE are well represented in the model. Velocity averaged from the bottom up to 100 m depth (Fig. 1) shows the signal of the ASC starting as a weak current in the Bellingshausen Sea and becoming a steady feature after the Ross Sea, which is consistent with generally accepted circulation schemes (see for instance Thompson et al. 2018). Other aspects of the circulation such as the inflow of CDW in the Amundsen Sea (e.g. Park et al. 2024) and the exchange of modified Warm Deep Water with DSW in the southern Weddell Sea (Ryan et al. 2017, Morrison et al. 2020) are also reproduced by the model.

In order to identify the model strengths and limitations we compare the results with a preliminary version of a climatology derived from the dataset prepared in the framework of OCEAN:ICE (Zhou et al. 2024). Salinity and Potential Temperature (PT) climatological values were averaged in the vertical to match the model layers. Unless otherwise stated, all model results presented are average values between 1990 and 2020. First circumpolar maps of S and PT are prepared for selected depths to give an overview of the model performance; difference maps are not prepared to avoid misinterpretation caused by interpolation errors. The circumpolar comparison continues for sea ice, where sea ice extent and sea ice concentration information from www.meereisportal.de are used (Spreen et al. 2008), and sea ice production from Kaleschke et al. (2024). Finally ice shelf basal melt is compared with a product derived from satellite observations (Paolo et al 2023).

For more quantitative conclusions we perform a regional analysis using a Temperature-Salinity (TS) Diagram with Binned Data Percentages. From the climatology grid we select points that have measurements in at least two different years and find the corresponding elements in the model, i.e. the triangle containing that point,

and calculate the mean profile between the three vertice nodes. In the vertical, the climatology is averaged to match the model depths. The results are presented in a TS diagram that shows the percentage of occurrence inside bins with 0.025 salinity interval and 0.05 potential temperature bins, with this method the most frequent water masses and their properties can be identified and compared more efficiently than in a usual TS diagram showing a cloud of points. This analysis is performed for four regions: Amundsen Sea, Ross Sea, Cooperation Sea, and Weddell Sea. The regions are divided in two sub areas: one onshore of the 1000 m isobath that is referred to as continental shelf for convenience and a second region between the 1000-3000 m isobaths, referred to as slope. For each of the regions, the whole water column (surface to bottom) is considered.

2.2.1 Circumpolar view

At 50 m depth, where waters are representative of the surface mixed layer, the temperature and salinity distributions are similar between the model and climatology (Fig. 3, panels on the left). Here, higher salinities and lower temperatures are seen over the continental shelves of the southern Weddell Sea and western Ross Sea, and a signal of enhanced salinity in Prydz Bay, Cooperation Sea, can also be seen in both model and climatology. At this depth the model is mainly colder and fresher than the climatology, with the exception of the southern Weddell Sea and western Ross Sea, where the model is slightly more saline. Locations of strong temperature gradients agree very well between the model and the climatology.

With the exception of the Weddell Sea, the cold bias seen at 50 m in the model is replaced by a warm bias at 100 m depth (Fig. 3, right panels), where the signal of the cold water formed during stronger winter convection that stays during summer (winter water - WW) should be seen in most of the circumpolar region. Except for this bias, the patterns seen in model and climatology are similar for temperature and salinity. In the model, the WW signal, colder temperatures, is stronger at 85 m depth (not shown). Even during winter months the cold waters reach only down to this depth in most open ocean areas around Antarctica. This underestimation of the WW depth is probably caused by the difficulty the model has to reproduce winter sea ice production in open ocean areas (Fig. 9).

Fig. 3: Comparison between temperature (top) and salinity (bottom) in climatology and model results at 50 m (on the left) and 100 m (right) depth.

A relatively warm water mass is found below the WW in the whole Southern Ocean. In most regions this water mass is referred to as Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), but in the Weddell Sea it is generally termed Warm Deep Water. For convenience here we use only CDW to refer to both. The main core of CDW is characterised by maximum temperature and high salinity. In the Ross Sea and the East Antarctic open ocean areas as well as on the Amundsen Sea continental shelf, the core of the CDW is warmer and fresher in the model than in the climatology (Fig. 5). Westward from Cooperation Sea (Prydz Bay) all the way to the South Scotia Ridge offshore of the 1000 m-isobath, the core of the CDW is found deeper and is fresher in the model than in the climatology; the same difference also stands out when comparing the climatology with the World Ocean Atlas (not shown), used as the model’s initial conditions.

Fig. 4: Comparison of temperature (left), salinity (right), and depth (bottom panels) of the CDW core (as defined by the depth of the temperature maximum in the water column) between climatology and model results.

The signal of the deeper CDW eastward of Cooperation Sea is reflected on the properties of the water flowing along the bottom resulting in a warmer bottom water in the model (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, inshore of that, i.e. over the continental shelf and the upper part of the slope, there is good agreement between the modeled and observed temperatures and salinities. The warm signature from the ASC is stronger in the model (Fig. 5,

right) where it separates the cold Weddell Sea Bottom Water (WSBW) found in the deep ocean from the water near the surface freezing point on the continental shelf . An analysis of snapshot fields (not shown) confirms that the model is able to replenish the waters in the Weddell Sea abyss with newly formed WSBW, however the signature of the process is lost in the long-term averaging. The bottom of the Bellingshausen and Amundsen seas is covered with warm waters that can cause strong basal melt when it is transported into the ice shelf cavities. Between the Amundsen and Ross Sea the model features warm bottom waters while in the climatology the bottom waters are colder. The HSSW signal in the western Ross Sea and Weddell Sea is present in both the climatology and in the model results. The ability to represent the HSSW suggests that the model is able to simulate strong sea ice production in the correct locations. In the following chapter we evaluate the sea ice part of the model.

Fig. 5: Comparison of bottom temperature (left), and salinity (right) between the climatology and model results.

2.2.2 Sea ice

The model reproduces the seasonal cycle of Antarctic sea ice extent reasonably well. Compared with the 1991-2020 average from www.meereisportal.de the maximum sea ice extent is overestimated by ~10 % in winter and underestimated in summer months (Fig. 6). The averaged spatial distribution in February (Fig.7, left) indicates that the model has difficulties in preserving the sea ice outside the Weddell Sea during summer, while the winter overestimation is related to a slight increase in sea ice extent all around Antarctica (Fig.7, right).

Fig. 6: Annual sea ice extent from observations (green curve) and model (purple dots).

Besides sea ice extent and the distribution of sea ice concentration, another important factor for the ocean is the amount and location of sea ice production. As described before, sea ice production is important to form HSSW, which in turn plays a crucial role for the interaction between the continental shelf, ice shelf cavities and the open ocean. Comparing the model with the sea ice production rates from Kaleschke et al. 2024 (OCEAN:ICE deliverable D1.4) (Fig. 8), the model is capable of reproducing the coastal polynyas observed during winter time but strongly underestimates the sea ice production in the open ocean. As mentioned before, this is the most likely explanation for the shallower WW in open ocean areas. During summer the satellite-derived product indicates sea ice formation in the coastal polynyas along the Ross and Ronne Ice Shelf fronts and in the southeastern Weddell Sea, whereas in the model summer sea ice formation is mostly confined to a small coastal polynya in the westernmost sector of the Ronne Ice Shelf.

Fig. 7: Model Sea ice concentration in February (left) and September (right). The red curves show the observed average sea ice extent from www.meereisportal.de

2.2.3 Ice Shelf Basal melt

Comparing FESOM2's ice shelf basal melt rates with the mean from a product derived from satellite observations (Paolo et al 2023) (Fig. 9) shows that the model is capable of representing the general pattern observed around Antarctica. Higher melt rates are observed in the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas in both products. For the Ross Ice Shelf, stronger melt is observed on the western side where HSSW is observed at the bottom; the satellite product indicates a few patches of freezing that are not seen in the model. Freezing is also indicated in certain places in East Antarctica, but the model only shows a small region of refreezing at Amery Ice Shelf. The model also simulates the intensified melting close to the Amery Ice Shelf grounding line.

In the Weddell Sea, the intensified melt at the grounding is also present at FRIS and Larsen C (Fig. 9). The model reproduces this feature for FRIS but the melt in Larsen C is stronger and concentrated on the southwestern sector of the ice shelf. In the model, melting is seen along the HSSW path from the Ronne polynya towards the grounding line in the south. Westward from that, along the Antarctic Peninsula, a freezing line extends from the ice shelf front all the way to the grounding line. In the satellite product, the HSSW melt path is only noticeable near the ice front, and the freezing signal is much weaker. In both, freezing occurs north of Henry Ice Rise, southwestward from Berkner Island.

Fig. 8: Sea ice production in February (top) and September (bottom) from satellite-derived products (Kaleschke et al. 2024, left) and model (right).

The net circumpolar freshwater flux from ice shelf basal melting is larger in the model than in the observations, 1812 Gt/year versus 1032 Gt/year. If we disregard the freezing areas and take only the basal melt into account the difference gets smaller, 1898 Gt/year versus 1381 Gt/year. More than half of this difference comes from the Amundsen Sea ice shelves, 646 Gt/year versus 366 Gt/year, a region that is subject to strong inflow of CDW.

Fig. 9: Ice shelf thickness change caused by basal melt from satellite-derived products (Paolo et al. 2024, left) and in the model (right)

2.2.4 Amundsen Sea

The presence of CDW over the Amundsen Sea continental shelf is evident in TS diagrams for both the model and the observations (Fig. 8), but within this water mass the bins with occurrences higher than 0.9 % in the climatology ($S=34.7$ with PT from 1.05 to 1.1°C) are saltier and colder than in the model ($S=34.65$ with PT from 1.05 to 1.2°C , and $S=34.625$ with $PT=1.15^{\circ}\text{C}$); unless otherwise stated the 0.9 % threshold is used for all values mentioned from now on. The warmer and more prominent core of CDW in the model can explain the higher ice shelf basal melt, which on the other hand leads to the freshening of the waters. Closer to the surface, the WW core in the climatology ($S=34.075$ with $PT=-1.65^{\circ}\text{C}$) is warmer and saltier than in the model ($S=34.025$ with $PT=-1.8^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Amundsen Sea CS

Fig. 10: Binned TS diagram from the Amundsen Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

On the slope (between 1000-3000 m depth) the CDW is saltier and has a larger temperature spread in the climatology (S from 34.7 to 34.725 with PT from 0.2 to 1.6°C) than in the model (S from 34.65 to 34.675 with PT from 0.35 to 1.55°C). The WW that mixes with CDW is not well defined, neither in the climatology nor in the model. In the climatology it only stands out using occurrence higher than 0.1 % as threshold (S from 34

to 34.15 with PT from -1.8 to -1.3 °C), in the model a threshold of 0.03 % is necessary and indicates a fresher WW core (S=34 with PT from -1.75 to -1.7 °C).

There is no indication of waters with AABW density in the Amundsen sea continental shelf or slope, whereas in the neighbouring basin of the Ross Sea, HSSW is indeed found on the continental shelf.

Fig. 11: Binned TS diagram from the Amundsen Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

2.2.5 Ross Sea

The HSSW over the Ross Sea continental shelf has a larger salinity spread in the model (S between 34.55 and 34.75 with PT between -1.95 and -1.8°C) than in the climatology (S between 34.7 and 34.75, PT between -1.95 and -1.8°C). Using a threshold of 0.05% occurrence, there is indication that HSSW mixes with WW, but the mixing line involves warmer waters in the climatology (S from 34.15 to 34.75 with PT from -2 to -1°C) than in the model (S from 34.05 to 34.75, PT from -2 to -1.4 °C). Using the same threshold, modified CDW (mCDW) in the climatology is warmer and saltier (S=34.675 with PT 0.3°C) than in the model (S = 34.65 with PT from -0.1 to 0.05 °C).

Fig. 12: Binned TS diagram from the Ross Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

On the continental slope, CDW is warmer and saltier in the climatology ($S= 34.675, 34.7$ with $PT = -0.15$ to 1.35 °C) than in the model ($S= 34.65$ to 34.675 with $PT = 0.2$ to 1.1 °C) and towards the bottom (larger density) it mixes with colder waters. With a threshold of 0.1%, WW has a larger spread in the model (S from 34 to 34.225 with PT from -1.85 to -1.5 °C) than in the climatology (S from 34.125 to 34.175 with PT from -1.8 to 1.7 °C), but the part of WW that mixes with CDW is saltier (and thus denser) in the climatology.

Fig. 13: Binned TS diagram from the Ross Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

2.2.6 Cooperation Sea

On the Cooperation Sea continental shelf, WW mixes mainly with HSSW and the product is colder and saltier in the climatology (S from 34.425 to 34.525 with PT from -1.95 to -1.85 °C) than in the model (S from 34.125 to 34.45 with PT from -1.9 to -1.5 °C). The mixing line between WW and CDW is also on the warmer side in the model but the warmest waters with threshold 0.05% are very similar in climatology ($S=34.675$ with PT from 0.25 to 0.55 °C) and model ($S=34.675$ with PT from 0.35 to 0.6 °C).

Fig. 14: Binned TS diagram from the Cooperation Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

The CDW on the continental slope is very similar to the warm water found on the continental shelf ($S=34.675$ with climatology PT from 0.1 to 0.7 °C, and model PT from 0.2 to 0.7 °C). In the climatology this water mixes with colder waters forming a colder and slightly fresher water ($S=34.65$ with PT from -3.5 to 0.45 °C), this mixture does not appear in the model. The mixing line between CDW and WW with 0.1% threshold is almost the same in both but the WW is colder in the model ($S=34.3$ with climatological PT from -1.75 to -1.55 °C and model PT from -1.8 to -1.65 °C).

Fig. 15: Binned TS diagram from the Cooperation Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

2.2.7 Weddell Sea

For the comparison between model and climatology the Weddell Sea was divided into 3 subregions: eastern Weddell Sea between the Prime Meridian and the Filchner Through, southern Weddell Sea in front of Filchner Ronne Ice Shelf, and northwestern Weddell Sea.

On the eastern Weddell Sea continental shelf (Fig. 16), the mCDW is colder in the climatology ($S=34.65$ with PT from 0.25 to 0.45 °C) than in the model (S from 34.625 to 34.675 with PT from 0.4 to 0.5 °C), indicating that in the model there is less influence of colder waters. On the slope (Fig. 17), CDW is warmer in the climatology (S from 34.65 to 34.675 with PT from -0.35 to 0.65 °C) but the contribution of cold waters is still missing in the model (S from 34.6 to 34.675 with PT from 0.3 to 0.55 °C).

In both areas, the WW is saltier in the climatology (continental shelf: S from 34.275 to 34.45 with PT from -1.9 to -1.8 °C and slope: S from 34.35 to 34.375 with PT -1.85 to -1.8 °C) than in the model (continental shelf: S from 34.05 to 34.325 with PT from -1.85 to -1.65 °C; and slope: S from 34.175 to 34.25 with PT from -1.85 to -1.8 °C). As a consequence, the mixing line between WW and mCDW happens along lower density.

Fig. 16: Binned TS diagram from the eastern Weddell Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

Fig. 17: Binned TS diagram from the eastern Weddell Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

In the southern Weddell Sea (Fig. 18), ISW is seen in both the climatology (S from 34.575 to 34.65 with PT = -2°C) and in the model (S from 34.55 to 34.725 with PT from -2 to -1.95 °C). In the model, the mixing line between ISW and WW (S from 34.125 to 34.55 with PT from -1.9 to -1.75 °C) stands out (occurrence higher than 0.9%) while in the climatology only WW is evident (S from 34.275 to 34.4 with PT from -1.9 to -1.75°C). Using a threshold of 0.2%, CDW appears in the climatology (S=34.65 with PT from 0.4 to 0.45 °C) and in the model (S from 34.65 to 34.675 with PT from 0.45 to 0.5 °C), but in the model it already shows with threshold of 0.5% (S=34.65 with PT =0.5 °C). The mixing between WW and CDW occurs at higher densities in the climatology on the continental shelf and on the slope, similar to the eastern Weddell Sea.

Fig. 18: Binned TS diagram from the southern Weddell Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

WW on the southern Weddell Sea slope (Fig. 19) is fresher in the model (model: S from 34.1 to 34.3 with PT from -1.9 to -1.8 °C, and climatology: S from 34.325 to 34.4 with PT from -1.85 to -1.7 °C). The CDW core is present in both (model: S from 34.6 to 34.675 with PT from 0.3 to 0.5 °C, and climatology: S from 34.65 to 34.675 with PT from -0.4 to 0.55 °C), here again the model fails to represent the coldest waters found towards the bottom.

Fig. 19: Binned TS diagram from the southern Weddell Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

The bottom waters are also misrepresented along the northwestern Weddell Sea slope (Fig. 21); the mixing line between CDW and AABW is cutoff at 0 °C in the model (S from 34.6 to 34.675 with PT from 0 to 0.55 °C) while in the climatology it reaches colder temperatures (S from 34.625 to 34.675 with PT from -0.8 to 0.5 °C). The mixing line between CDW and WW is less dense in the model for the same reasons stated before, i.e. WW is fresher in the model (model: S from 34.35 to 34.375 with PT from -1.85 to -1.8 °C and climatology: S from 34.425 with PT from -1.8 to -1.75 °C).

The northwestern Weddell Sea continental shelf (Fig. 20) is mainly occupied by WW, mCDW and the mixture between them. Consistent with the other regions, the modelled WW is fresher (S from 34.3 to 34.4 with PT from -1.85 to -1.2 °C) than in the climatology (S from 34.4 to 34.5 with PT from -1.75 to -1.2 °C). The mCDW

is warmer in the model (model: S from 34.575 to 34.65 with PT from -0.15 to 0.05 °C and climatology: S from 34.55 to 34.6 with PT from -1 to -0.45 °C).

Fig. 20: Binned TS diagram from the northwestern Weddell Sea continental shelf from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

Fig. 21: Binned TS diagram from the northwestern Weddell Sea slope from the climatology (left) and the model (right).

In general, processes on the Weddell Sea continental shelf are well reproduced by the model. HSSW is formed in the Ronne polynya and enters the Ronne Ice Shelf cavity, where it causes melt and forms ISW, waters colder than the surface freezing point, as it flows towards the Filchner Ice Shelf. Although not present in the climatologies, model monthly means and observations (Janout et. al. 2021) show that some ISW can leave the cavity through Filchner Through. Together with HSSW formed in front of Berkner Island it mixes with ambient waters to produce the DSW pool. The exchange between DSW and mCDW, observed at the intersection of Filchner Through and the shelf break (Darelius et. al. 2023), is evident in the velocity (Fig. 1) and bottom temperature (Fig. 5) fields and the signature of both water masses is seen in the TS diagram (Fig. 18).

Although the thermohaline signal of DSW gets lost on the slope, GMW is carried down the slope along the bottom (Fig. 22) indicating that the processes involved in the formation of AABW and its precursors are, at

least partially, reproduced in the model. At the end of the simulation, after 52 years (1968-2020), the GMW distribution from all ice shelves (Fig. 22 left) shows that the downslope flow occurs in different regions around Antarctica while the contribution only from Filchner Ronne Ice Shelf (Fig. 22 right) shows the path of the DSW formed in the southern Weddell Sea. A detailed analysis of the contribution of the GMW tracers from different regions is planned in OCEAN ICE.

The initial conditions might play an important role for the misrepresentation of the deep ocean properties. Interpolating the relatively coarse PHC climatology, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ in horizontal resolution and 33 vertical levels, onto a high-resolution grid can create some unrealistic features, especially on the slope where big differences are expected over small distances. Most of these features are ‘eroded’ and ‘cured’ by the model. However, one apparent artefact in contrast to the climatology is the presence of warmer and saltier waters in the model initial conditions at the bottom of the continental shelf and upper slope in East Antarctica, as well as in the southern and the northwestern Weddell Sea.

The warmer bottom waters may be one of the reasons for the absence of DSW on the slope. Another explanation proposed is that to properly resolve this process with Z coordinate, the model needs to be eddy resolving (Wang et al. 2008) at the location. Considering scales of the first baroclinic Rossby radius derived from WOA (Fig. 2.7 in Ryan 2018) would require a circumpolar resolution higher than 1.5 km, on the whole continental shelf where the Rossby radius is around 3 km. This is not feasible with the resources available to date.

Fig. 22: Glacial meltwater concentration at the bottom from all ice shelves (left) and from FRIS (right) at the end of the simulation. Only values higher than 0.001% are shown.

1. 2.2.8 Summary

The model is able to reproduce the main circulation patterns all around Antarctica. Key processes and characteristics, including the production of HSSW and its interaction with ice shelves to cause basal melt or

create the supercooled ISW, are also accounted for in the model. In general, the WW in the model is fresher, most likely related to the model's difficulties to reproduce sea ice formation in the open ocean during winter, whereas excessive sea ice melting during summer may be an additional factor.

The fresher WW leads to a lighter water when mixing with CDW or mCDW. These lighter waters might have an effect on the DSW properties, especially during its journey along the continental shelf towards the deep ocean. Although sea ice is almost everything for a good representation of the continental shelf and upper layer, other factors are important as previously mentioned.

The addition of the GMW tracers proved to be of great importance since they provide an alternative to the classical thermohaline analysis to show that the model is able to represent the formation of AABW.

2.3 References

Antonov, J., Levitus, S., Boyer, T. P., Conkright, M. E., O'Brien, T., & Stephens, C. (1998). World ocean atlas 1998. Volume 1, Temperature of the Atlantic Ocean.

Boyer, T. P., Levitus, S., Antonov, J. I., Conkright, M. E., O'Brien, T. D., & Stephens, C. (1998). World ocean atlas 1998. Volume 4, Salinity of the Atlantic Ocean.

Danilov, S., Sidorenko, D., Wang, Q., and Jung, T. (2017) The Finite-volume Sea ice–Ocean Model (FESOM2), *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 10, 765–789, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-765-2017>

Danilov, S., Q. Wang, R. Timmermann, N. Iakovlev, D. Sidorenko, M. Kimmritz, T. Jung, and Schröter, J. (2015), Finite-Element Sea Ice Model (FESIM), version 2, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 8, 1747–1761, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1747-2015>

Darelius, E., Daae, K., Dundas, V., Fer, I., Hellmer, H. H., Janout, M., ... & Østerhus, S. (2023). Observational evidence for on-shelf heat transport driven by dense water export in the Weddell Sea. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 1022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36580-3>

Harada, Y., Kamahori, H., Kobayashi, C., Endo, H., Kobayashi, S., Ota, Y., ... & Takahashi, K. (2016). The JRA-55 Reanalysis: Representation of atmospheric circulation and climate variability. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan*. Ser. II, 94(3), 269-302. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2016-015>

Hellmer HH, Olbers DJ. (1989) A two-dimensional model for the thermohaline circulation under an ice shelf. *Antarctic Science*. 1989;1(4):325-336. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102089000490>

Janout, M. A., Hellmer, H. H., Hattermann, T., Huhn, O., Sültenfuss, J., Østerhus, S., ... & Kanzow, T. (2021). FRIS revisited in 2018: On the circulation and water masses at the Filchner and Ronne ice shelves in the southern Weddell Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 126(6) . <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JC017269>

Kobayashi, S., Ota, Y., Harada, Y., Ebata, A., Moriya, M., Onoda, H., Onogi, K., Kamahori, H., Kobayashi, C., Endo, H., Miyaoka, K., Takahashi, K., 2015. The JRA-55 reanalysis: general specifications and basic characteristics. *J. Meteorol. Soc. Jpn.* 93, 5–48. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2015-0>.

Morrison, A. K., Hogg, A. M., England, M. H., & Spence, P. (2020). Warm Circumpolar Deep Water transport toward Antarctica driven by local dense water export in canyons. *Science Advances*, 6(18), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aav2516>

- Nakayama, Y., R. Timmermann, C. B. Rodehacke, M. Schröder, and H. H. Hellmer (2014), Modeling the spreading of glacial meltwater from the Amundsen and Bellingshausen Seas, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 41, 7942–7949, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL061600>
- Paolo, F., Gardner, A. S., Greene, C. A. & Schlegel, N. (2024). *MEaSURES ITS_LIVE Antarctic Quarterly 1920 m Ice Shelf Height Change and Basal Melt Rates, 1992-2017*. (NSIDC-0792, Version 1). [Data Set]. Boulder, Colorado USA. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center. <https://doi.org/10.5067/SE3XH9RXQWAM>.
- Park, T., Nakayama, Y. & Nam, S. Amundsen Sea circulation controls bottom upwelling and Antarctic Pine Island and Thwaites ice shelf melting. *Nat Commun* **15**, 2946 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47084-z>
- Ryan, S., T. Hattermann, E. Darelius, and M. Schröder (2017), Seasonal cycle of hydrography on the eastern shelf of the Filchner Trough, Weddell Sea, Antarctica, *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans*, 122, 6437–6453, doi:[10.1002/2017JC012916](https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC012916).
- Ryan, S. (2018). On the Flow of Modified Warm Deep Water toward the Filchner Ronne Ice Shelf, Weddell Sea, Antarctica (Doctoral dissertation, Universität Bremen).
- Schaffer, J., Timmermann, R., Arndt, J. E., Kristensen, S. S., Mayer, C., Morlighem, M., and Steinhage, D. (2016) A global, high-resolution data set of ice sheet topography, cavity geometry, and ocean bathymetry, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 8, 543–557, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-8-543-2016>,
- Schubert, R., Thompson, A. F., Speer, K., Schulze Chretien, L., and Bebieva, Y. (2021) The Antarctic Coastal Current in the Bellingshausen Sea, *The Cryosphere*, 15, 4179–4199, <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-15-4179-2021>,
- Spreen, G., L. Kaleschke, and G. Heygster (2008), Sea ice remote sensing using AMSR-E 89-GHz channels, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 113, C02S03, doi:[10.1029/2005JC003384](https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JC003384).
- Steele, M., R. Morley, and W. Ermold, 2001: PHC: A Global Ocean Hydrography with a High-Quality Arctic Ocean. *J. Climate*, 14, 2079–2087, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2001\)014%3C2079:PAGOHW%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014%3C2079:PAGOHW%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Thompson, A. F., Stewart, A. L., Spence, P., & Heywood, K. J. (2018). The Antarctic Slope Current in a changing climate. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 56, 741–770. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018RG000624>
- Wang, Q., Danilov, S., and Schröter, J. (2008). Comparison of overflow simulations on different vertical grids using the Finite Element Ocean circulation Model. *Ocean Modelling*, 20 (4), 313–335, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2007.10.005>
- Zhou, S., Dutrieux, P., Giulivi, C. (2024). Southern Ocean (90°S–45°S) conservative temperature and absolute salinity profiles compilation (OCEAN ICE D1.1). SEANOE. <https://doi.org/10.17882/99787>

2.4 Open Science

We are considering adding the climatological results as part of the visualisation and interaction tools supported by Ocean Ice (<http://www.soosmap.aq/>) or to make them only available to download in a data platform. At the moment, they are available for anyone interested upon request. The temperature and salinity climatology is being prepared for publication and will be available soon, the remaining data used are freely available online. The procedures used for validation are described in the text and can be reproduced accordingly.

A manuscript addressing the temporal variability in the model is in preparation and will partly be based on the analysis performed in the current document.

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

The evaluation of the model presented in this manuscript is the first step towards using it to assess how the ocean controls the heat and freshwater delivery to and from ‘cold’ (e.g. Weddell Sea) as well as ‘warm’ (Amundsen Sea) sites of ice sheet-ocean interaction around Antarctica, and the processes that control mixing, water mass formation and export over the continental shelves and subpolar basins. Next to demonstrating the strengths of the model, this evaluation also addresses the model’s limitations and caveats.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

This deliverable contributes by showing that a good representation of water mass pathways onto the continental shelf can lead to a good representation of hydrography and basal melt rates under warm- and cold-water ice shelves. Sea ice formation seems to be crucial to the properties of waters that flow into the cavity. Increased sea ice formation produces HSSW that can flow under the ice shelf and cause melt, but on the other hand, it can block or erode the flow of warm water. Decreasing volumes of HSSW facilitate mCDW water access to the cavity.